

CROSS-CULTURAL ADJUSTMENT: IMPACT OF SELF-CONSTRUALS

Dr. V. SELVALAKSHMI

Assistant Professor (O.G), Department of MBA, SRM Valliammai Engineering College, Kattankulathur.

Dr. S. P. S. ARUL DOSS

CEO, Gnanam Business School, Tanjavore.

Dr. S. RAMACHANDRAN

Deputy Director, SRM Group, Kattankulathur.

Abstract:

Internationalization of education has created global platforms for students to explore new culture and gain knowledge from best educational institutions. On the flipside, these international students experience lots of social interaction and issues. Social Relationships experienced by international students in a global platform far from their home depends a lot on the person's cultural orientation which can affect their social relationships. This present study examines the influence of demographic factors on the self-construal factors of international students, explored interdependent dimensions of self-construal, perception of international students towards the various dimensions of self-construal and at last how it's impacting psychological adjustment of international students. Total 499 participant's responses were collected. Factor analysis was conducted to extract the factors (independent and interdependent) categories of self-construal scale. Relationship between the independent and interdependent factors on psychological adjustment of international students was examined. Result obtained inferred that autonomy, direct communication, being unique and competition moderately helps the international students towards better adjustment in host environment while sociability, harmony & conformity also influenced them in better adjustment.

Keywords: International Students, Self-construal, Interdependence, Independent, cross-cultural adjustment.

INTRODUCTION:

Globalization is a 'progression that highlights on the overall progression of thoughts, assets, individuals, economy, culture, information, values, merchandise, administrations, and innovation', while internationalization of advanced education is depicted as 'the way toward coordinating a worldwide, intercultural and worldwide measurement of objectives, instructing/learning, research and administration elements of a college or advanced education framework' (Jane Knight, 2014).

Upsurge of International student's movement globally influenced globalization, economic wealth and continuously changing relocation/migration patterns in global platform. An OECD report predicts that 8 million students will choose to study out of their home country by 2025 (ICEF 2017). Another report by ICEF 2015 clearly states the surge in volume of international students between 1990 and 2014. Some of the countries do not have sufficient infrastructure for higher education, hence students from these countries look out for better opportunities and choose to study abroad (ICEF 2017).

MIGRATION OF INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS IN INDIA

Countries perceive international students in a different way depending on the status of the visa in their own country and their residence status. Kritz (2015) Basically, international students are those who seek temporary residence on some purpose as students, exchange program for teachers and also as researchers in a country other than their place of permanent residence (Nuffic 2012; Rajkhowa 2014 and OCED (2012). The various situations pertaining to politics, economy, social security and academic pose challenges to the students moving abroad temporarily for the duration of their education, the duration usually varies from a year to a couple of years. The figures indicating migration of international students to other countries is ever increasing worldwide despite the various challenges as mentioned herein? These challenges are also tested, the ability of the students to face and struggle with issues or some claims thus enabling them to grab the developmental opportunities.

As per AISHE statistics during 2015-16, only 1% of the international student population is represented as enrolled in India, the figure standing at 45, 424. However, post 2000, Huffington post, this strength has increased manifold five times. Consequently, India is anticipated to be the world's biggest destination (119 million) for college students (The wire, 2017). However, as per the statement by Mr. Prakash Javadekar, Human Resource Development Ex-minister of India, this figure has remained stagnated during 2019 and the focus of these students has shifted to countries like Australia and Singapore (National 2019). To explore this change of mindset of the students and to explore the cause behind it, this study is most important.

Diaspora of International students representation in India are majorly from Nepal (23.6 percentage), Afghanistan (.9.3 percentage), Bhutan (4.8 percentage). Nigeria and Sudan constitutes (4.4 percentages) each (AISHE 2017).

Table 1.1 Top ten countries contributing to International students Diaspora in India

S.No	Countries Name	No of students
1	Nepal	9574
2	Afghanistan	4404
3	Bhutan	2925
4	Nigeria	2090
5	Sudan	2059
6	Malaysia	1901
7	United Arab Emirates	1479
8	Iran	1459
9	Yemen	1238
10	Srilanka	1189

Source: Huffingtonpost.in

International student's enrolment for advanced education in India has extended significantly in the most recent era. In this examination, universal students' encounters are inspected in

psychological and sociocultural settings. Through idiosyncratic meetings, the various researches discovered that global students manage the acculturation like academic difficulties, social separation, and social alteration. In particular, scholarly and psychological difficulties included communication and adjustment with others. Thus, they need to manage social disengagement when participating in various gathering exercises. Socially, they have to go up against the various perspectives for studying in India. To beat these difficulties, students have incorporated support within themselves and from different external forces from the college to defeat these difficulties. Therefore, as exhibited in this study, these international student's difficulties can be solved by offering sufficient support. The college should be set up to meet students' psychological as well as social requirements.

Ward and Kennedy (1991) investigate the influence of psychological and socio-cultural adjustment during cross-cultural adoption. One hundred and seventy-eight New Zealand American Field Service students dwelling in 23 unique nations finished polls which contained appraisals of the accompanying: Personality (extraversion and locus of control); life changes (Social Readjustment Rating Questionnaire); achiness to visit the family, cultural separation, acculturation (cultural character and cultural integration-separation); frames of mind toward host nation; language capacity; measure of contact with host and conational; relationship fulfilment with co-nationals and receiving family; results in proportions of socio-cultural (social trouble) and mental adjustment (Profile of Mood Status). Stepwise suppressions uncovered that achiness to visit the family, outside locus of control, life changes, and social trouble represented 55% of the difference in psychological adjustment. Conversely, cultural separation, language capacity, fulfilment with host national contact, cultural separation and mind-set aggravation clarified 52% of the fluctuation in socio-cultural adjustment. In the second piece of the exploration, mental and socio-cultural adjustment of American Field Service students studied among 142 locally situated New Zealand students. In spite of the fact that there were no noteworthy contrasts in psychological adjustment between the two gatherings, the students who were occupant abroad experienced more prominent socio-cultural troubles than the student's inhabitant in New Zealand.

Sandhu and Asrabadi (1994) in their research identified stress experienced by the international students and new strategies which might help them during the adoption to new culture. The researchers could likewise utilize this scale to look at the encounters of acculturative stress of remote students of different ethnic gatherings and utilize that data to survey the adequacy of advising procedures. Further studies to verify validity and reliability should be undertaken based on this study. Basically, there are two major contributions of this scale. In the first place, this scale is intended to evaluate in a far reaching way the acculturative stress of remote students. Second, it measures this acculturative pressure which could encourage open doors for progressively exact research. The pleasant experiences of foreign students such as joy, stimulation, and accomplishments of personal and educational goals are not included on purpose. It is not that foreign students do not have such positive experiences, but that the major concerns of mental health practitioners are their retention, academic success and satisfaction with time spent in the host country.

Toshiaki Furukawa (1997), investigated about the impact of deliberate social separation on the mental change of global students when studying abroad. This investigation through CDQ survey, bifurcated in two parts, included 211 students from secondary and undergraduate level. Before leaving home country, MPI survey was carried out and GHQ during stay in host country. A CDQ survey was again conducted on returning back to their home country from host country. This study demonstrated that the psychological distress was greater with greater cultural distance faced by the students when in the host country of study

The researchers Ward and Rana (1999) identified the cultural adjustment of foreign students to another culture. The article closes with an appraisal of correspondence factors adding to acculturation among workers. Correspondence is seen as the major basic procedure just as a result of the acculturation process. In an investigation of 104 remote inhabitants in Nepal, Ward and Rana-Deuba (1999) analyzed acculturation modes among the dimensions of host nation has relationship to psychological and sociocultural adjustment. Solid co-national recognizable proof anticipated upgraded psychological prosperity while solid host national ID was related with better sociocultural adjustment. The connection among psychological and sociocultural adjustment changes as indicated by the conditions of acculturation—the relationship increments with closeness to or integration of the host culture. Utilizing Berry's four acculturation techniques (1997), the individuals who received an integrated style experienced essentially less mental trouble than others. Respondents who favoured the assimilation style revealed less social trouble. The study observed integration to be a versatile acculturation as best solution.

Guan and Dodder (2001) researched; in a comparative build to Berry's model, looked at the effect of cross cultural contact on qualities and personality on 107 Chinese students in the U.S. versus 185 Chinese students in China. Four dimensions were found: group integration, self-protection, cultural preservation and social integration. The scientists anticipated that Chinese students in China should score higher on every one of the qualities since contact with the U.S. culture would probably lessen the significance of the dimensions among the U.S. gathering. No huge distinction was found in the social integration dimension. Out of the blue, the China gathering scored lower in social gathering integration and self-protection. They scored higher in cultural preservation as anticipated. As of study, acculturation research has revealed that correspondence is certifiably not a point of convergence. Analysts have inspected the connection among acculturation and ethnic change, parental objectives; character attributes and worries among different factors. They additionally keep on growing new models of acculturation. The findings have shown that acculturative stress level significantly based on the term period, how long the international students stay in host country. The study has shown that with increasing duration of stay student experience less acculturative stress.

Yeh and Inose (2003) explored and founded that various factors such as age, Fluency of English, social support fulfilment and social connectedness as indicators of acculturative stress. The research findings were based on study among sample of 359 foreign students. Results show that universal students from Europe experienced less acculturative stress than

their partners from Asia, Central/Latin America, and Africa. In addition, English familiarity, social help fulfilment, and social connectedness were all indicators of acculturative stress. Suggestions of research talked about International students faces extra troubles as they frequently battle with achiness to go home, lost common social backings during the adjustment time frame and language troubles which all go about as a boundary to creating significant network systems.

Babiker et al. (1980) explains about the PCD as a measure of distress experienced by sojourners during the acculturation process. A cultural distance index was developed by the authors to measure an individual difference of the discrepancies perceived between social and physical aspects of home and the environment of the host. In another study involving foreign students in Scotland, it measures the adjustments on psychological level. On the other hand, perceived cultural distance(PCD) outweighed acculturation orientations in a study among Russian exchange students (Galchenko & Van de Vijver, 2007).

Hwang and Ting (2008), research inspects the effect of level of acculturation and acculturative stress on the psychological well-being of Asian American students. Progressive relapse investigations were utilized to explain the connection between level of acculturation, acculturative stress, and emotional well-being (psychological distress and clinical discouragement). Being less related to standard United States culture was related with higher psychological distress and clinical gloom however lost noteworthiness when acculturative stress was brought into the model. Maintenance or giving up of distinguishing proof with one's legacy culture was not related with psychological well-being results. Understanding degree of acculturation can enable us to distinguish those in danger, discoveries recommend that acculturative stress is a progressively proximal hazard factor and expands chance for psychological wellness issues autonomously as an impression of stress.

Yanyin Zhang Yinan Mi (2010) discovered boundless and steady English language challenges experienced by non English-talking international students in their academic studies in nations like Australia. The study uncovered that English language issues did not genuinely influence the scholarly exhibition of certain samples in Australia and that most of the language troubles did not last past 2 years. It additionally demonstrated that students were clear about what their primary issues were and what aptitudes were generally pivotal for their scholastic investigations. The discoveries of the study show obviously that strong value made accessible by international students. The international students concentrating on their courses which they have been enrolled seeks high proficiency expertise knowledge on the corresponding course. Besides, the cultural foundation, the international students should be considered when planning course curriculum considering students' earlier learning knowledge and the status of English in their nations, which may bring about various issues or issues in various zones (e.g., Bradley and Bradley, 1984). Concerning Chinese students, accommodated in different nations improving their tuning in and talking abilities in the initial 2 years or something like that, also, for the academic composition ability on an on-going premise. At last, to make the best use of the value of students and to empower students, it is

necessary that curriculum should not just support to finish their graduation, but in addition, like Australia, English language necessities in college curriculum should be set deliberately.

Zuria Mahmud et.al (2010) examined about the difficulties experienced by IS in Malaysia. Information was gathered by conducting common interviews with these students from different nations studying at three self-financed colleges and subjects, which incorporate culture, atmosphere, and care. Discoveries of the study give direction to college executives in Malaysia to improve arrangements in accepting international students. International students in Malaysia face adjustment with respect to culture, atmosphere, and care. A couple of variables are found to enable International students to more readily change. These incorporate, recognition and likeness of culture, language capacity, what's more, productive administrations at the establishment. Malaysian colleges ought to improve administrations to compliment the high quality foundation. Proficient international workplaces, multicultural prepared student staff, and backing projects worked for international students will help to improve administrations for international students. College language focuses should be enabled to guarantee that international students secure their language capacity before joining the scholastic projects. On the student's part, great execution in both neighborhood language and English language help international students to find out about neighborhood culture and to empower them take advantage of their study involvement in Malaysia.

SELF-CONSTRUAL AND CROSS-CULTURAL ADJUSTMENT

Self-construal denotes the degree to how much oneself is characterized independent of others or reliant with other persons. At first, the term got from apparent cultural contrasts in oneself. Westerners are thought to have an autonomous self-interpretation, which is described by separateness from others, by regard for one's capacities, characteristics, inclinations, and wishes, and by the power of one's individual objectives over those of in-gatherings. East Asians are thought to have a reliant self-understanding, which is portrayed by a feeling of crucial connectedness with others, and by the primacy of group goals over one's individual goals. Social and cultural psychologists now view these as three dimensions of the self, which virtually all people construct to some degree.

It is believed that people from the west have their own interpretation of self and are separate from others by features of their characteristics, wishes, inclinations and their capacities. The individual's objective is viewed as powerful compared to others. Comparatively, people from East Asia are believed to be self-understanding and could easily connect with others in terms of the in-gatherings of one's job. The primary concern is a group goal rather than the goal of an individual. Hence, these three self-dimensions are built by most people and are viewed as important by psychologists in social and cultural arena.

Figure 1.4 Dimensions of Self-construal

The research by Cheng Lu Wang proposed three self-construal dimensions related to cross cultural adjustment: (a) self-other association, (b) dependence, and (c) self-orientation. The self-other association dimension alludes to one's observation of the self as either a particular personality or a persistent connection among self as well as other people. X Researchers have recognized that the individuals tend to see the self as a part of the gathering and other people who will in general see the self as an augmentation/separate from the in-gathering (Triandis et al., 1988). The dependence dimension is characterized by as the dependence of one individual on others or as an individual who feels confident and independent.

Finally, the self-orientation dimension alludes to objectives and accomplishments: regardless of whether one's psychological exercises and practices are primarily centered around internal (i.e., individual) goals or on social (i.e., aggregate) goals. The individualistic self-orientation is about, one's individual objectives or individual accomplishments, which are normally assessed by inner measures. The aggregate self-orientation revolves around group objectives or gathering accomplishments, which are estimated by the internal objectives of reference gatherings/group's objectives. Predictable with Singelis (1994), some individual might be generally progressively associated on certain dimensions, and, simultaneously, increasingly isolated from others. Empirical proof bolster the fact that, there seems considerable differences in self-construal both at the cultural level as well as among genders.(Wang and Mowen, 1997).

Most significant, there is motivation to accept that various dimensions of Kashima et al. (1995) who explored both cultural and gender orientation best depict the gathering contrasts inside everyone. They found that contrasts among Western and Eastern cultures were increasingly articulated on individualistic or aggregate dimensions of the self, like our self-direction dimension of self-construal. In non-Western cultures, one's close to home or individualistic objectives might be subordinate to one's group objectives, at the same time feel of self-satisfaction occurs, when the individual tends to satisfy goals/tasks related to pertinent others (Markus and Kitayama, 1991; Triandis, 1989). The self-dimension of dependence doesn't clearly define the cultural differences (Bochner, 1994; Kashima et al., 1995). Markus and Oyserman (1989) recommended that men folk see them self as discrete,

with distinction acknowledged through the boundary of limits between oneself as well as other people, while for women the referent is the "self-in-connection" with others.

As per Kitayama (1991), Independence and interdependence are the two dimensions to self-construal. These two dimensions describe how much each individual relate themselves as isolated or associated with others. An Independent self-construal personality would distance self from a group mainly because of their individuality, ego and restricting oneself within their own boundary. On the other hand, Interdependence personalities are less isolated from others and are progressively associated. This research study considers the two dimensions of self-construal specified by Kitayama (1991). Self-construal and cross-cultural adjustments have been related by a conceptual connection by various researchers (e.g., Cross 1995; Yang., 2006). Yamaguchi and Wiseman (2001) examined Japanese international students studying in U.S and found the strong independent self-construal were able to adjust better, and people with independent self-construal are positively related with increased level of contact and intercultural communication effectiveness which implies a better socio-cultural adjustment for international students.

SELF CONSTRUAL SCALE

Null hypothesis H₀: There is no significant influence of (a) Gender (b) Course (c) Experience in living India (d) Duration of stay of India (e) Martial Status on Self Construal

Table 4.21 Influence of demographic variables on Self Construal

	Classification	N	Mean	S D	F-value
Gender	Male	310	3.61	0.447	7.072** (p=.008)
	Female	189	3.72	0.447	
Course	Under graduation	366	3.52	0.467	6.207** (p=.000)
	Graduation and above	133	3.81	0.569	
Experience in living India	Yes	411	3.67	0.423	1.220 (p=.270)
	No	88	3.61	0.559	
Duration of stay of India	Less than 1 year	83	3.79	0.456	15.500** (p=.000)
	1 year	94	3.69	0.440	
	2 years	41	4.03	0.289	
	3 years	101	3.41	0.415	
	4 years	148	3.61	0.428	
	More than 4 years	32	3.72	0.385	
Martial status	Single	483	3.65	0.453	3.772* (p=.024)
	Married	36	4.02	0.329	

*Significant at 5% level **Significant at 1% level

- **Gender**

In the Table 4.21, F value 7.072 shows it is significant; therefore the null hypothesis H_0 3(a) is rejected at 1% level. Female respondents have scored highest mean value of 3.72 and the lowest mean value is scored by male respondents (3.61). This shows that female International students possess better understanding skills than the male respondents.

- **Course**

In the Table 4.21, F value 6.207 shows it is significant; therefore the null hypothesis H_0 3(b) is rejected at 1% level. Respondents with above graduation level education have scored highest mean value of 3.81 and the lowest mean value is scored by respondents of under graduates (3.52). This shows that the respondents with Graduation and higher degrees are possessing better self construal level than under graduates.

- **Experience in Living India**

In the Table 4.21, F value 1.220 shows it is insignificant; therefore the null hypothesis H_0 3(c) is accepted at 5% level. This shows that the experience in living India is not significantly influencing the Self Construal.

- **Duration of stay in India**

In the Table 4.21, F value 15.500 shows it is significant; therefore the null hypothesis H_0 3(d) is rejected at 1% level. Respondents staying two years in India have scored highest mean value of 4.03 and the lowest mean value is scored by respondents staying three years in India (3.41). This shows that respondents living one year in India for studying are more self construal and respondents staying three years in India are little self construal. Post hoc test in the Table 4.22 shows the difference between the groups of stay in India towards the Psychological adjustment.

Table 4.22: Post hoc test for difference in duration of stay in India with regard to Self Construal

Duration of stay in India	Subset for alpha = 0.05			
	1	2	3	4
3 years	3.41			
4 years		3.61		
1 year		3.69	3.69	
More than 4 years		3.72	3.72	
Less than 1 year			3.79	
2 years				4.03
p-value	1.000	0.170	0.219	1.000

Subset-1 in Table 4.22 exhibits that the respondents' duration of stay in India for one year have significant differences towards self construal with other groups. However the respondents staying in India for four years, one year, and more than one year are in the second subset has significant difference with other groups regarding self construal.

Respondents staying in India for one year, more than 4 years and less than one year in third subset and 2 years in the fourth subset have significant difference with other respondents and have high level of self construal.

- **Marital status**

In the Table 4.21, F value 3.772 shows it is significant; therefore the null hypothesis $H_0 3(e)$ is rejected at 5% level. Married respondents have scored highest mean value of 4.02 and the lowest mean value is scored by respondents living as single (3.65). This shows that married International students have better level of self understanding than the unmarried respondents who possess relatively lesser self construal.

INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS PERCEPTION ABOUT SELF-CONSTRUAL:

Foreign student's perception about the self construal scale is measured through thirty eight variables. Through exploratory factor analysis thirty eight variables are reduced to eight factors which are grouped under two categories by four factors in both Independent and Interdependent dimensions. The factors explored are shown as below:

1. Autonomy
2. Direct communication
3. Uniqueness
4. Competition
5. Relatedness
6. Sociability
7. Belonging
8. Harmony and Conformity

Out of eight dimensions shown first four dimensions Autonomy, Direct communication, Uniqueness and Competition are grouped under Independent and last four dimensions Relatedness, Sociability, Belonging and Harmony and Conformity are grouped under interdependent.

4.4.1 Exploratory Factor Analysis for Self Construal Scale

Factor analysis is the process that reduces the numerous variables into factors. In this process the variables are converted into prime factors according to the correlations between the variables and this is done through statistical background. The perception studies relies on the respondents responses in five point Likert scales. The assignment of numerical values in five point Likert scales for each variable develops co-variances and the variables in the same domain. These co-variances and correlation coefficients are useful statistical parameters which groups likely variables to form an inventive factor. This is established by Exploratory Factor Analysis through Principal Component Method in vari-max rotation. Based on the closest relationships between the variables the variables are grouped into the factors. The factors are named after seeing the components of the variables. In this section the variables measured in the self construal independent and interdependent scales are factor analysed.

4.4.1.1 Factor analysis for Independent Self construal scale

The KMO measures for sampling is recorded as 0.911, Bartlett's test of sphericity (Approx Chi-square 463.254, $p < .001$) shows applying factor analysis is suitable for the data. Table 4.9 presents the Eigen value and variances explored by the factors are presented.

Table 4.9 Eigen values and variance explored by the factors of Self construal independent scales

Factors	Initial Eigen values		
	Eigen Value	Percentage of Variance	Cumulative Percentage
1	14.32	37.62	37.62
2	9.36	12.36	49.98
3	2.18	10.31	60.29
4	1.96	7.36	67.65

From the Table 4.9, it is inferred that nineteen variables measured under the Self construal independent scales are reduced into four distinct factors. The factors explored 37.62, 12.36, 10.31 and 7.36 are the percentage of variances respectively. It is also noted that the cumulative percentage explored by these four factors account for 67.65%. The factors explored along with the components' factor scores are presented in the Table 4.10.

Table 4.10 Factor scores of Self construal independent scales

Factor	Components	Factor Scores
Factor1: Autonomy	For me being a lively imaginative person is significant.	0.804
	Having the option to deal with myself is an essential worry for me.	0.761
	I want to act naturally dependent as opposed to subordinate upon others	0.645
	Whenever I set a goal for myself, I usually highly focus on it and do my best to achieve the goal	0.601
	Having autonomy over my life is most important	0.544
Factor 2: Direct Communication	I better say no than being understood wrongly.	0.801
	I want to be immediate and frank when managing individuals I've quite recently met	0.762
	Conversing during a class isn't an issue for me	0.711
	I generally express my opinions	0.632
	I generally express my considerations straightforwardly when I speak with others	0.579
Factor 3: Uniqueness	I voice my own opinions during discussions among group members	0.536
	I enjoy being unique and different from others in many aspects	0.789
	I appreciate being respected for my unique characteristics	0.765
	Having my own character free of others is essential to me	0.662
Factor 4: Competition	It is significant for me to keep my uniqueness when I am in gathering	0.598
	I aim at being a competitive person in my field (Academics)	0.798
	I will in general compete with others when I'm associated with a gathering venture	0.732
	I generally put forth a valiant effort when I compete with others	0.642
	Performing superior to others in allotted tasks is significant for me	0.533

From the Table 4.10 it is inferred that factor 1 is a combination of five variables such as “For me being a lively imaginative person is significant.”, “Having the option to deal with myself is an essential worry for me. ”, “I want to act naturally dependent as opposed to subordinate upon others”, “Whenever I set a goal for myself, I usually highly focus on it and do my best to achieve the goal” and “Having autonomy over my life is most important” which is named as Autonomy (Aut) factor.

Factor 2 is a combination of five variables such as “I’d rather say “No” directly, than risk being misunderstood”, “I want to be immediate and frank when managing individuals I’ve quite recently met”, “Conversing during a class isn’t an issue for me”, “I generally express my opinions” and “I generally express my considerations straightforwardly when I speak with others” which is named as Direct communication (Dir Commⁿ) factor.

Factor 3 is a combination of four variables such as “I enjoy being unique and different from others in many aspects”, “I appreciate being respected for my unique characteristics”, “Having my own character free of others is essential to me” and “It is significant for me to keep my uniqueness when I am in gathering” which is named as Uniqueness (Uniq) factor.

Factor 4 is a combination of four variables such as “I aim at being a competitive person in my field (Academics)”, “I will in general compete with others when I’m associated with a gathering venture”, “I generally put forth a valiant effort when I compete with others” and “Performing superior to others in allotted tasks is significant for me” which is named as Competition (Comp) factor.

Lively imagination, risk in understanding, enjoy being unique and different from others in many aspects and expecting themselves as competitive person in my academic field are the important aspects that contribute to the Independent Self construal.

4.4.1.2 Factor analysis for Interdependent Self construal scale

The KMO measures for sampling are recorded as 0.927, Bartlett’s test of sphericity (Approx Chi-square 514.212, $p < .001$) shows applying factor analysis is suitable for the data. Table 4.11 presents the Eigen value and variances explored by the factors are presented.

Table 4.11 Eigen values and variance explored by the factors of Self construal interdependent scales

Factors	Initial Eigen values		
	Eigen Value	Percentage of Variance	Cumulative Percentage
1	15.31	38.61	38.61
2	8.34	13.34	51.95
3	3.15	11.28	63.23
4	1.58	8.32	71.55

From the Table 4.11, it is inferred that nineteen variables measured under the Self construal interdependent scales are reduced into four distinct factors. 38.61, 13.34, 11.28 and 8.32 are the percentage of variances explored by the factors respectively. It is also noted that the

cumulative percentage explored by these four factors account for 71.55%. The factors explored along with the components' factor scores are presented in the Table 4.12.

Table 4.12 Factor scores of Self construal interdependent scales

Factor	Components	Factor Scores
Factor 1: Relatedness	I prefer and give importance to relationships with others/friends compared to my own achievements.	0.736
	When I consider myself, I frequently think about my companions or my family	0.701
	While being among the group, I watch my words so I won't annoy anybody	0.689
	It is significant for me to feel associated with my campus life	0.551
Factor 2: Sociability	Having a social life is vital for me	0.722
	More often than not I appreciate participating in group exercises than individual exercises	0.629
	I like to impart easily details to my companions	0.603
	I generally attempt endeavors to communicate with others appropriately	0.574
	I attempt endeavors to improve my social abilities	0.509
Factor 3: Belonging	Feel of security, when being an accepted member in a group is significant to me.	0.762
	It is significant for me to have a feeling of having a place in my place where I study	0.733
	I have a desire to be part of gathering or association or group	0.608
	I appreciate being a part of a gathering or association	0.522
Factor 4: Harmony and Conformity	I am careful to maintain harmony in my group	0.801
	While being among the group, I watch my words so I won't annoy anybody.	0.756
	I have regard for the my professors/higher authorities/collage mates with whom I interface	0.681
	It is significant for me to respect choices made by the group members	0.654
	I truly accept my folks' recommendation into thought when settling on significant life choices	0.521
	Even though I am not happy being a part of group, If situation requires me, I will be definitely the part of the group	0.509

From the Table 4.12, Factor 1 is a combination of four variables such as “I prefer and give importance to relationships with others/friends compared to my own achievements.”, “When I consider myself, I frequently think about my companions or my family”, “While being among the group, I watch my words so I won't annoy anybody” and “It is significant for me to feel associated with my campus life” which is named as Relatedness factor.

Factor 2 is a combination of five variables such as “Having a social life is vital for me”, “More often than not I appreciate participating in group exercises than individual exercises”, “I like to impart easily details to my companions”, “I generally attempt endeavours to

communicate with others appropriately” and “I attempt endeavours to improve my social abilities” which is named as Sociability factor.

Factor 3 is a combination of four variables such as “Feel of security, when being an accepted member in a group is significant to me.”, “It is significant for me to have a feeling of having a place in my place where I study”, “I have a desire to be part of gathering or association or group”, and “I appreciate being a part of a gathering or association” which is named as Belonging factor.

Factor 4 is a combination of six variables such as “I am careful to maintain harmony in my group”, “While being among the group, I watch my words so I won’t annoy anybody”, “I have regard for the my professors/higher authorities/collage mates with whom I interface”, “It is significant for me to respect choices made by the group members ”, “I truly accept my folks’ recommendation into thought when settling on significant life choices” and “Even though I am not happy being a part of group, If situation requires me, I will be definitely the part of the group ” which is named as Harmony and Conformity factor.

Felt like relationships with others are more important than their own accomplishments, possessing considerable degree of social life, security of being an accepted member of a group and careful to maintain harmony in their group is the important aspect that contributes to the Interdependent Self construal.

Influence of Demographic Variables on Self Construal

Foreign student’s demographic variables may influence Self Construal. One-way ANOVA is used to study whether the influence of demographic variables on Self Construal is significant. Duncan’s post hoc test is used to find the difference between the groups regarding Self Construal. Table 4.21 shows the results of one-way ANOVA for the influence of demographic variables on Self Construal.

Relationship between Self Construal Scale and Psychological Adjustment

This section reveals the relationship between Self construal scale (independent and interdependent) and Psychological adjustments. Relationship between Self construal scale and Psychological adjustments is identified as significant by using Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation. The correlation coefficient identified along with their p-values is displayed in the Table 4.33.

Null hypothesis H_0 : There is no significant relationship between

- (i) Autonomy
- (ii) Direct communication
- (iii) Uniqueness
- (iv) Competition and Psychological adjustment

Null hypothesis H₀9: There is no significant relationship between

- (i) Relatedness
- (ii) Sociability
- (iii) Belonging
- (iv) Harmony and Conformity and Psychological adjustment

Table 4.33 Relationship between Self construal scale and Psychological adjustment

	Psychological adjustment	
	r-value	p-value
Independent		
Autonomy	0.321**	.002
Direct communication	0.415**	.000
Uniqueness	0.428**	.000
Competition	0.524**	.000
Interdependent		
Relatedness	0.352**	.000
Sociability	0.456**	.000
Belonging	0.269*	.015
Harmony and Conformity	0.278*	.011

*Significant at 5% level **Significant at 1% level

4.5.9.1 Self construal scale (independent)

It is evident from the results in the Table 4.33, significant relationship between Autonomy and Psychological adjustment is inferred, the null hypothesis H₀8 (i) is rejected. The relationship exist is moderate and Positive (r = 0.321, p=.002). Hence it is concluded that the Autonomy of the International students getting educated in India moderately helps in Psychological adjustment.

It is inferred from the results in the Table 4.33, significant relationship between Direct communication and Psychological adjustment is observed, the null hypothesis H₀8 (ii) is rejected. The relationship exist is Positive (r=0.415, p=.000). Hence it is concluded that the direct communication of the International students getting educated in India considerably improves their Psychological adjustment.

It is evident from the results in the Table 4.33, significant relationship between Uniqueness and Psychological adjustment is inferred, the null hypothesis H₀8 (iii) is rejected. The relationship exist is positive (r=0.428, p=.000). Hence it is concluded that the Uniqueness of the International students getting educated in India enhances Psychological adjustment.

It is inferred from the results in the Table 4.33, significant relationship between Competition and Psychological adjustment is observed, the null hypothesis H₀8 (iv) is rejected. The relationship exist is positive (r=0.524, p=.000). Hence it is concluded that the Competition of the International students getting educated in India considerably develops the Psychological adjustment.

4.5.9.2 Self construal scale (Interdependent)

It is evident from the results in the Table 4.33, significant relationship between Relatedness and Psychological adjustment is inferred, the null hypothesis H_{09} (i) is rejected. The relationship exist is moderate and Positive ($r=0.352$, $p=.000$). Hence it is concluded that the Relatedness of the International students getting educated in India moderately helps in Psychological adjustment.

It is inferred from the results in the Table 4.33, significant relationship between Sociability and Psychological adjustment is observed, the null hypothesis H_{09} (ii) is rejected. The relationship exist is Positive ($r=0.456$, $p=.000$). Hence it is concluded that the Sociability of the International students getting educated in India considerably improves their Psychological adjustment.

It is evident from the results in the Table 4.33, significant relationship between Belonging and Psychological adjustment is inferred, the null hypothesis H_{09} (iii) is rejected. The relationship exist is positive and minimal ($r=0.269$, $p=.015$). Hence it is concluded that the Belonging of the International students getting educated in India minimally helps in Psychological adjustment.

It is inferred from the results in the Table 4.33, significant relationship between Harmony and Conformity and Psychological adjustment is observed, the null hypothesis H_{09} (iv) is rejected. The relationship exist is positive and minimal ($r=0.278$, $p=.011$). Hence it is concluded that the Harmony and Conformity of the International students getting educated in India minimally helps in Psychological adjustment.

Findings and Discussions for Self Construal Scale

Factor of Independent Self construal are identified as:

- ✓ Autonomy
- ✓ Direct Communication
- ✓ Uniqueness
- ✓ Competition

Lively imagination, risk in understanding, enjoy being unique and different from others in many aspects and expecting themselves as competitive person in my academic field are the important aspects that contribute to the Independent Self construal.

Factors of Interdependent Self construal are identified as:

- ✓ Relatedness
- ✓ Sociability
- ✓ Belonging
- ✓ Harmony and Conformity

Relationships with others are more important than their own accomplishments, possessing considerable degree of social life, security of being an accepted member of a group and careful to maintain harmony in their group are the important aspect that contribute to the Interdependent Self construal.

- Setting the goal, focusing on it and giving the best is the important aspect of autonomy. International students agreed that lively imagination, autonomy over their life and they are not depending on others and they are self-reliant are the other aspects that contributes to the autonomy. However the respondents denied that ability in taking care of themselves is not a primary concern for them.
- Respondents' agreement showed that they are clear in stating their opinion is the important aspect of direct communication. Respondents agreed that they can express their thoughts directly while communicating/interacting to others, prefer to be direct and forthright when dealing with people that they have just met and able to express anything directly without taking any risk in understanding are the other aspects that contribute .However the students agreed that they have issues in speaking up during the class hours.
- Unique enjoyment and different from others in many aspects is the important feature of uniqueness. Respondents agreed that it is important for them to keep their uniqueness when they are in group. But they denied that they are not that much succeeded in establishing their personal identity which is independent of others and they are not being admired for their unique qualities.
- Respondents agreed that they are bringing their best while competing with others is the important aspect of competition. Giving better perform better than others when task is assigned and tend to compete with others when involved with a group project are the other aspects that contributed to the competition. But the respondents denied that they are not able to be a competitive person in academic field as they expected.
- Students' response revealed that thinking about friends and family while thinking about them is the important aspect of relatedness. Respondents accepted that their relationships with others are important to them to justify themselves and they frequently have the feeling that their relationships with others for their own accomplishments. But respondents denied that feeling connected to their campus life is not that much important.
- Students' response reveals that taking efforts to interact properly with others is the important aspect of sociability. Responses also revealed that the students are engaged most of the times in enjoying themselves in group than individual activities and at the same time they share little things with their friends. But the respondents denied that they showed less importance in having considerable degree of social life and takes less efforts to enhance their social skills.

- Students agreed that enjoyment being a part of a group or organization is the important aspect of belonging. Feel like belonging in their department where they study and willing to belong to a certain group or organization are the other aspects that contribute to the belonging. But the respondents agreed that they are not able to feel secured as recognized by the group.
- Respondents felt that they have due respect for their faculties/higher officials/classmates with whom they use to interact is the main aspect of harmony and conformity. Consideration of parents' advice while making important life decisions, giving respect to the decisions made by the group and careful in maintaining harmony in their group where they use to involve are the other aspects that contributes to the factor harmony and conformity. However, the respondents denied that they are not willing to stay in a group even they felt discomfort with the group and they watch their words even they offend anyone.
- Influence of gender, education, duration of stay in India and marital status on self construal are found significant. However experience living in India is not having any significant influence. Female International students possess better understanding skills than the male respondents. Respondents with graduation and higher degrees are possessing better self construal level than under graduates. Respondents living one year in India for studying are more self construal and respondents staying three years in India are little self construal. Married International students are having better level of self understanding than the unmarried respondents who possess relatively lesser self construal.

Relationship between Interdependent Self construal and Psychological Adjustment:

- Significant relationship between autonomy and psychological adjustment is inferred, the null hypothesis is rejected. The relationship exist is moderate and positive ($r = 0.321$, $p=.002$). Hence it is concluded that the autonomy of the International students getting educated in India moderately helps in psychological adjustment.
- Significant relationship between direct communication and psychological adjustment is observed. The relationship exist is positive ($r=0.415$, $p=.000$). Hence it is concluded that the direct communication of the International students getting educated in India considerably improves their psychological adjustment.
- Significant relationship between uniqueness and psychological adjustment is inferred. The relationship exist is positive ($r=0.428$, $p=.000$). Hence it is concluded that the uniqueness of the International students getting educated in India enhances psychological adjustment.
- Significant relationship between competition and psychological adjustment is observed. The relationship exist is positive ($r=0.524$, $p=.000$). Hence it is concluded

that the competition of the International students getting educated in india considerably develops the psychological adjustment.

- Significant relationship between relatedness and psychological adjustment is inferred, the null hypothesis $H_0(i)$ is rejected. The relationship exist is moderate and positive ($r=0.352$, $p=.000$). Hence it is concluded that the relatedness of the International students getting educated in India moderately helps in psychological adjustment.
- Significant relationship between sociability and psychological adjustment is observed. The relationship exist is positive ($r=0.456$, $p=.000$). Hence it is concluded that the sociability of the International students getting educated in India considerably improves their psychological adjustment.
- Significant relationship between belonging and psychological adjustment is inferred. The relationship exist is positive and minimal ($r=0.269$, $p=.015$). Hence it is concluded that the belonging of the International students getting educated in India minimally helps in psychological adjustment.
- Significant relationship between harmony and conformity and psychological adjustment is observed. The relationship exist is positive and minimal ($r=0.278$, $p=.011$). Hence it is concluded that the harmony and conformity of the International students getting educated in India minimally helps in psychological adjustment.

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